

Evaluation Materials for a Comparative Analysis of Process Mining Tools for IoT-Centric Process Intelligence

Tilen Tratnjek and Gregor Polančič

Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, University of Maribor, Koroška cesta 46, Maribor 2000, Slovenia.

Apromore Platform

Environment

Operating system:

- Windows 11 Pro
- Version: 21H2
- OS build: 22000.2538

Web browser:

- Brave 1.81.135
- Chromium: 139.0.7258.127

Version:

- Online. Version 10.3

License:

- Academic

Dataset:

- An IoT-Enriched Event Log for Process Mining in Smart Factories [1].

Documentation review

Data Management

Apromore supports importing BPMN, CSV, PARQUET, XES, XLSX, ZIP, and GZ files, as well as accessing online resources via HTTPS and cloud services like Dropbox, Google Drive, and OneDrive. It offers advanced filtering, data pipelines with preview and scheduling, direct connections to external sources Amazon S3, and anonymization for compliance [2], [3].

Score: 5. According to documentation, Apromore imports multiple file types and connects to cloud services and Amazon S3. It supports anonymization, advanced filtering, and pipelines with scheduling. Setup can be complex, but the scope of supported sources and automation meets full coverage criteria.

Process Discovery

Apromore visualizes process flows with graphical elements where line thickness and color indicate frequencies. It supports process maps and BPMN views enriched with perspectives such as frequency, duration, cost, and rework. Users can inspect cases, variants, and activities, apply advanced filtering, and export results as images, JSON, or BPMN models for reuse.

Score: 5. Documentation shows Apromore provides graphical process maps and BPMN models enriched with perspectives such as frequency, duration, and cost. Users can filter activities, inspect cases, and export models for reuse. The breadth of perspectives and export options aligns with full functionality [2], [3].

Conformance Checking

Apromore compares BPMN reference models with event logs to detect deviations, violations, and modelling inconsistencies. Deviations are highlighted visually and quantified through conformance metrics, enabling objective assessment of where and how processes diverge. Users can filter variants and inspect specific cases to explore deviations in detail. The checker does not support certain BPMN constructs such as event-based and complex gateways, link events, or boundary events [2], [3].

Score: 5. Based on documentation review, Apromore compares BPMN models against event logs, quantifies deviations, and highlights inconsistencies. Users can explore variant-level detail. Some BPMN constructs are not supported, but the overall coverage and structured metrics align with established conformance checking practices.

Process Analysis

Apromore allows adjusting model complexity for different abstraction levels and supports multiple analysis perspectives such as frequency, duration, and cost. Bottlenecks can be identified through simulation with token movement, highlighting areas of delay or accumulation. The tool also supports KPI definition and monitoring, linking process execution with organizational objectives. In addition, Apromore enables training predictive machine learning models on event logs to forecast case outcomes and remaining time, extending analysis into predictive domains [2], [3].

Score: 5. Documentation indicates Apromore provides analysis perspectives (frequency, duration, cost), bottleneck detection with simulation, and KPI monitoring. It extends into predictive domains by enabling machine learning models to forecast outcomes. Predictive performance depends on configuration and data quality, but coverage across descriptive, diagnostic, and predictive domains meets the full support definition.

Monitoring and Reporting

Apromore integrates dashboards with KPIs and metrics for effective process monitoring. The interface provides intuitive access to performance information and supports exporting data and visualizations in multiple formats. The tool also enables automatic generation of

reports and, in the full version, predictive monitoring based on machine learning models trained on historical data [2], [3].

Score: 5. According to official resources, Apromore includes dashboards with KPIs, automated reporting, and export options. The commercial version also enables predictive monitoring. While features vary by edition, the documented functionality supports both reactive and proactive monitoring scenarios.

Support

Apromore provides extensive documentation with clear terminology and comprehensive visual material, supporting quick onboarding and consistent learning. The commercial license includes training programs for different user levels and access to consultants who combine technical expertise with business knowledge. The tool also integrates an LLM-based copilot to assist in interpretation, though this is not included in the academic version [2], [3].

Score: 5. Documentation confirms Apromore provides extensive learning resources, commercial training programs, consulting and, advanced support features such as LLM-based assistants. The breadth of structured assistance justifies the highest score.

Task-based Evaluation

Question 1

Field	Description																																																							
Question	<i>What is the most frequent path in Smart Factory process that does not result in failure and includes at least two activities (excluding start/end activities)?</i>																																																							
Answer	The most frequent path with at least two activities contains 16 activities, has an average duration of 10.06 minutes, and appears in 12 cases (5.5% of all cases).																																																							
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discover process from log in home folder. 2. Open filter panel. 3. Exclude cases where <i>lifecycle = failure</i>. 4. Open case variants view and locate the most frequent variant with at least two activities. 																																																							
Output Type	Process map and table																																																							
Clarity/Interpretability	5 – Output is immediately understandable. Tables and visuals are clearly labelled, and the structure makes it easy to identify the relevant variant.																																																							
Effort	It has taken 10 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.																																																							
Ease of Use	5 – The interface is intuitive and consistent. Filtering and identifying the path required minimal interaction.																																																							
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot displays the 'apromore' interface. At the top, there is a process map with various activity nodes. Below it is the 'Case Variant Inspector' window, which contains a table with the following data:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Case variant ID</th> <th>Activity instances</th> <th>Average duration</th> <th>Cases</th> <th>Percentage (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>46.67 secs</td><td>14</td><td>6.42</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>16</td><td>10.06 mins</td><td>12</td><td>5.5</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3</td><td>2.83 mins</td><td>10</td><td>4.59</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4</td><td>2.43 mins</td><td>9</td><td>4.13</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5</td><td>2.97 mins</td><td>8</td><td>3.67</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>14</td><td>13.52 mins</td><td>7</td><td>3.21</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>14</td><td>8.25 mins</td><td>6</td><td>2.75</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>13</td><td>11.76 mins</td><td>6</td><td>2.75</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>19</td><td>16.56 mins</td><td>5</td><td>2.29</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>13</td><td>10.35 mins</td><td>5</td><td>2.29</td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Below the table, there is a pagination control showing '1 / 2' and a 'Download page' button.</p>	Case variant ID	Activity instances	Average duration	Cases	Percentage (%)	1	1	46.67 secs	14	6.42	2	16	10.06 mins	12	5.5	3	3	2.83 mins	10	4.59	4	4	2.43 mins	9	4.13	5	5	2.97 mins	8	3.67	6	14	13.52 mins	7	3.21	7	14	8.25 mins	6	2.75	8	13	11.76 mins	6	2.75	9	19	16.56 mins	5	2.29	10	13	10.35 mins	5	2.29
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Evaluator Notes	The filter modal must remain open to view variants. It cannot be resized, only moved, which may reduce usability on smaller screens.																																																							

Question 2

Field	Description
Question	<i>How many different process variants do exist in Smart Factory?</i>
Answer	140 process variants.
Steps taken	1. Discover process from log in home folder. 2. Locate number of case variants in toolbar.
Output Type	Text
Clarity/Interpretability	5 – The value is immediately visible, well-labelled, and requires no interpretation.
Effort	It has taken 2 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	5 - The function is self-explanatory and easy to access. No friction or ambiguity.
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows the 'Process discoverer' interface for 'MainProcess'. It features a toolbar with various icons and a search bar. Below the toolbar, there are several gauges and filters. The 'Case variants' gauge is highlighted, showing a value of 140/140. A yellow '6.5' label is visible near the gauge. The interface also displays various filters and statistics, including 'Cases', 'Case variants', 'Activity instances', and 'Activity'.</p>
Evaluator Notes	The variability ratio text uses yellow (#fba525) on white, which fails WCAG contrast standards and could reduce readability on smaller screens.

Question 3

Field	Description
Question	<i>Which variant has the longest average execution time from start to end in the Smart Factory with at least two cases?</i>
Answer	The longest variant contains 19 activities, with an average duration of 17.18 minutes. It has 6 cases, representing 1.99% of all cases.
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discover process from log in home folder. 2. Open case variants view. 3. Sort variants by average duration (descending). 4. Identify the variant with the longest average execution time.
Output Type	Process map and table
Clarity/Interpretability	4 – Average duration is clearly displayed for each variant, but interpretation requires converting decimal minutes to seconds.
Effort	It has taken 4 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	5 – The interface is intuitive, sorting is simple, and the required information is grouped logically. Few steps are needed, and navigation is straightforward.
Screenshot or Output	<p>The screenshot displays the 'Case Variant Inspector' window. It features a table with the following columns: Case variant ID, Activity instances, Average duration, Cases, and Percentage (%). The table is sorted by average duration in descending order. The variant with ID 9 is highlighted, showing 19 activity instances, an average duration of 17.18 mins, 6 cases, and 1.99% of total cases. The interface includes a search bar, pagination controls (1 / 2), and a 'Download page' button. Below the table, there is a section for 'apromore' with a process map visualization.</p>
Evaluator Notes	The filter modal issue noted in Q1 remains, but it did not affect the current task. The process map was not required to answer the question.

Question 4

Field	Description
Question	<i>What is the average number of activities per case in the Smart Factory process?</i>
Answer	The average number of activities per case is 10.49 .
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discover process from log in home folder. 2. Open filter panel. 3. Select <i>Performance</i> menu item. 4. Choose <i>Case length</i> in the performance measure dropdown. 5. Read the value.
Output Type	Text, visualization, and graph.
Clarity/Interpretability	5 – Numbers are clearly labelled and supported with visual aids. The output is immediately understandable, though the font size for values is somewhat small.
Effort	It has taken 6 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	5 – The measure is easy to locate, presented with interactive visuals, and requires minimal user action. Navigation is straightforward and consistent.
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows a software interface for analyzing process logs. The title bar reads 'Filter log: MainProcess'. The interface is divided into a left sidebar and a main content area. The sidebar contains navigation icons for 'Case', 'Event', 'Attribute', 'Case variant', 'Case ID', 'Timeframe', 'Performance', 'Path', 'Rework', and 'Blocks'. The main content area features a 'Performance measure' section with a dropdown menu set to 'Case length'. Below this, there are radio buttons for 'Retain' (selected) and 'Remove'. To the right, there are input fields for 'From' (0 %) and 'To' (100 %). A horizontal bar chart shows the distribution of case lengths, with a color gradient from green (Low) to red (High). Summary statistics are displayed: Min: 1, Median: 12, Average: 10.49, Max: 23, Total: 3,157. Below the bar chart is a histogram with a blue bar chart showing the frequency of case lengths. At the bottom, there are input fields for 'From 1' and 'To 23', along with 'Cancel' and 'OK' buttons.</p>
Evaluator Notes	

Question 5

Field	Description															
Question	<i>Which activity shows the highest deviation in its execution duration across cases in the Smart Factory?</i>															
Answer																
Steps taken																
Output Type																
Clarity/Interpretability																
Effort																
Ease of Use																
Screenshot or Output	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Case duration</th> <th>Case cost (N/A)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Average</td> <td>10.06 mins</td> <td>N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Min - Max</td> <td>8.51 mins - 16.77 mins</td> <td>N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Timeframe</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p> Average: 10.06 mins Std. dev: 2.18 mins First quartile: 8.96 mins Median: 9.27 mins Third quartile: 10.12 mins Min: 8.51 mins Max: 16.77 mins Total: 2.01 hrs Rework: 26.23 mins </p>		Case duration	Case cost (N/A)	Average	10.06 mins	N/A	Min - Max	8.51 mins - 16.77 mins	N/A	Total			Timeframe		
	Case duration	Case cost (N/A)														
Average	10.06 mins	N/A														
Min - Max	8.51 mins - 16.77 mins	N/A														
Total																
Timeframe																
Evaluator Notes	The tool does not provide a direct measure across all cases. Each of the 140 variants would need to be checked manually to identify the one with the highest standard deviation.															

Question 6

Field	Description												
Question	<i>What is average time for case completion in Smart Factory?</i>												
Answer	8.68 minutes.												
Steps taken	1. Discover process from log in home folder. 2. Locate average case duration in toolbar.												
Output Type	Text												
Clarity/Interpretability	5 - The duration is prominently displayed, clearly labelled, and requires no additional interpretation.												
Effort	It has taken 2 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.												
Ease of Use	5 – The value is highly visible and easy to locate. No friction or ambiguity.												
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows the 'Process discoverer' interface for 'MainProcess'. It features a toolbar with various filters and a summary panel on the right. The summary panel displays the following data:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">Case duration</th> <th>Case cost (N/A)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Average</td> <td>8.68 mins</td> <td>N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Min - Max</td> <td>instant - 48.11 mins</td> <td>N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>1.81 days</td> <td>N/A</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Below the summary panel, a 'Timeframe' is shown as '23 Jun 21, 15:32'.</p>	Case duration		Case cost (N/A)	Average	8.68 mins	N/A	Min - Max	instant - 48.11 mins	N/A	Total	1.81 days	N/A
Case duration		Case cost (N/A)											
Average	8.68 mins	N/A											
Min - Max	instant - 48.11 mins	N/A											
Total	1.81 days	N/A											
Evaluator Notes													

Question 7

Field	Description
Question	<i>How many cases have a total duration longer than twice the average case duration in Smart Factory?</i>
Answer	25 cases (8.2% of total cases).
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discover process from log in home folder. 2. Open filter panel. 3. Select <i>Performance</i>. 4. Enter 16.96 (twice the average case duration) in <i>Greater than or equal to</i> field. 5. Read result.
Output Type	Text
Clarity/Interpretability	5 – The number of cases is prominently displayed, well-labelled, and requires no additional interpretation.
Effort	It has taken 6 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	5 – The workflow is self-explanatory and the interface clear. The task was completed without friction.
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows the 'Process discoverer' interface for 'MainProcess'. It features a navigation bar with 'Process map' and 'BPMN model' tabs. Below the navigation bar, there are several filters and controls: 'Abstract by Case frequency' (set to High), 'Nodes' (100), 'Arcs' (10), and 'Parallelism' (40). The main area displays four circular gauges representing different metrics: 'Cases' (8.3%, 25/301), 'Case variants' (16.4%, 23/140), 'Activity instances' (12.9%, 408/3.2k), and 'Activity' (85.7%, 18/21). To the right, there is a table with columns for 'Case duration' and 'Case cost (N/A)'. The 'Case duration' table shows an average of 24.20 mins, a min-max range of 17.09 mins - 48.11 mins, and a total of 10.08 hrs. The 'Case cost' column is empty.</p>
Evaluator Notes	

Question 8

Field	Description																																																							
Question	<i>Which is the longest path for a case in Smart Factory.</i>																																																							
Answer	The longest path contains 23 activities .																																																							
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discover process from log in home folder. 2. Open case variants view. 3. Sort by duration to identify the variant with the longest path. 																																																							
Output Type	Table and process map																																																							
Clarity/Interpretability	5 – The table is well-labelled, columns are clearly visible, and the output is immediately interpretable.																																																							
Effort	It has taken 4 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.																																																							
Ease of Use	5 – Sorting the case variants table makes the result easy to find with minimal interaction. The workflow is intuitive and quick.																																																							
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows a table titled "Case Variant Inspector" with the following data:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Case variant ID</th> <th>Activity instances</th> <th>Average duration</th> <th>Cases</th> <th>Percentage (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>41</td><td>23</td><td>28.37 mins</td><td>1</td><td>0.33</td></tr> <tr><td>40</td><td>23</td><td>48.11 mins</td><td>1</td><td>0.33</td></tr> <tr><td>42</td><td>21</td><td>15.27 mins</td><td>1</td><td>0.33</td></tr> <tr><td>45</td><td>20</td><td>14.63 mins</td><td>1</td><td>0.33</td></tr> <tr><td>43</td><td>20</td><td>16.06 mins</td><td>1</td><td>0.33</td></tr> <tr><td>44</td><td>20</td><td>15.36 mins</td><td>1</td><td>0.33</td></tr> <tr><td>46</td><td>20</td><td>12.83 mins</td><td>1</td><td>0.33</td></tr> <tr><td>47</td><td>19</td><td>18.61 mins</td><td>1</td><td>0.33</td></tr> <tr><td>48</td><td>19</td><td>18.18 mins</td><td>1</td><td>0.33</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>19</td><td>17.18 mins</td><td>6</td><td>1.99</td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Navigation: « < 1 / 2 > » [1 - 100 / 140]</p> <p>Click on a case variant to inspect it Download page</p>	Case variant ID	Activity instances	Average duration	Cases	Percentage (%)	41	23	28.37 mins	1	0.33	40	23	48.11 mins	1	0.33	42	21	15.27 mins	1	0.33	45	20	14.63 mins	1	0.33	43	20	16.06 mins	1	0.33	44	20	15.36 mins	1	0.33	46	20	12.83 mins	1	0.33	47	19	18.61 mins	1	0.33	48	19	18.18 mins	1	0.33	9	19	17.18 mins	6	1.99
Case variant ID	Activity instances	Average duration	Cases	Percentage (%)																																																				
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Evaluator Notes																																																								

Question 9

Field	Description
Question	<i>To what extent do cases under process model WF_101 comply with the defined process model WF_101?</i>
Answer	There are 14 process variants for 34 cases under WF_101, resulting in 41.2% variability. According to tools thresholds, below 20% is good, 20–40% acceptable, and 40–60% alarming. Of these, 12 cases (35.29%) fully comply with the model. Deviations appear partly due to the event log using a generic transport activity instead of distinct labels (e.g., <i>transport_from_A_to_B</i> vs. <i>transport_from_B_to_A</i>). This causes apparent deviations even when execution is correct.
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Right-click process event log and create new filtered log. 2. In <i>Attribute</i> dropdown, select <i>process_model_id</i> and filter for WF_101. 3. Open both the filtered event log and the WF_101 process model. 4. Run conformance check. 5. Read results.
Output Type	Conformance visualization with graphical interface for filtering.
Clarity/Interpretability	5 – The visualization is clear, deviations are easy to identify, and a legend supports interpretation.
Effort	It has taken 8 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	4 – Creating a filtered log before running conformance adds friction, but the workflow remains manageable with relatively few steps.

<p>Screenshot or output</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Case Variant</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>35.29%</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>11.76%</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>11.76%</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>5.88%</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5.88%</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>5.88%</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>2.94%</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>2.94%</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>2.94%</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>2.94%</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>2.94%</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>2.94%</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>2.94%</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>2.94%</td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Right click on a case variant to see its details</p>	Case Variant	Percentage	1	35.29%	2	11.76%	3	11.76%	4	5.88%	5	5.88%	6	5.88%	11	2.94%	7	2.94%	12	2.94%	9	2.94%	8	2.94%	13	2.94%	10	2.94%	14	2.94%
Case Variant	Percentage																														
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8	2.94%																														
13	2.94%																														
10	2.94%																														
14	2.94%																														
<p>Evaluator Notes</p>	<p>Apromore requires unique activity names for conformance. In Smart Factory logs, repeated generic activities (e.g., <i>pick_up_and_transport</i>) caused errors: “Unable to check conformance. The model has nodes with the same name.” The issue was resolved by renaming activities in the model, though this introduced some false-positive deviations. Importantly, the adjustment could be made within Apromore without external tools.</p>																														

Question 10

Field	Description																																	
Question	<i>What is the most common activity in the Smart Factory process and how often does it occur?</i>																																	
Answer	The most common activity is /vgr/pick_up_and_transport with 917 occurrences (29.05%).																																	
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discover process from log in home folder. 2. Open <i>Activity</i> view. 3. Sort activities by frequency. 4. Read values. 																																	
Output Type	Table																																	
Clarity/Interpretability	5 – The table is clear, well-labelled, and immediately understandable. Column headings are distinct and consistent.																																	
Effort	It has taken 4 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.																																	
Ease of Use	5 – The workflow is self-explanatory. Sorting and reading results required no friction.																																	
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows a software interface titled 'filter log MainProcess'. It features a sidebar with navigation options: Case, Event, Attribute, Timeframe, Performance, Frequency, Path, and Between. The main area is divided into several sections: 'Events' with 'Retain' and 'Remove' options; 'Attribute' with a dropdown set to 'Activity'; 'Attribute condition' with a dropdown set to 'Activity'; 'Event performance' with a 'Duration' dropdown set to '0 Days'; and 'Matching' with 'Any value' selected. Below these is a table with columns for 'Value', 'Activity instances', and 'Frequency'. The table lists various activities, with '/vgr/pick_up_and_transport' at the top, having 917 instances and 29.05% frequency. Other activities include /hbw/unload (299 instances, 9.47%), /hbw/store_empty_bucket (263 instances, 8.33%), /wt/pick_up_and_transport (259 instances, 8.2%), /ov/burn (238 instances, 7.54%), /hw/human_review (174 instances, 5.51%), /men/debur (141 instances, 4.47%), /hbw/get_empty_bucket (134 instances, 4.24%), /sm/transport (131 instances, 4.15%), and /hbw/store (122 instances, 3.86%). The interface includes pagination controls at the bottom showing '1 / 1' and '1 - 21 / 21', along with 'Cancel' and 'OK' buttons.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Value</th> <th>Activity instances</th> <th>Frequency</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> /vgr/pick_up_and_transport</td> <td>917</td> <td>29.05%</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> /hbw/unload</td> <td>299</td> <td>9.47%</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> /hbw/store_empty_bucket</td> <td>263</td> <td>8.33%</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> /wt/pick_up_and_transport</td> <td>259</td> <td>8.2%</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> /ov/burn</td> <td>238</td> <td>7.54%</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> /hw/human_review</td> <td>174</td> <td>5.51%</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> /men/debur</td> <td>141</td> <td>4.47%</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> /hbw/get_empty_bucket</td> <td>134</td> <td>4.24%</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> /sm/transport</td> <td>131</td> <td>4.15%</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> /hbw/store</td> <td>122</td> <td>3.86%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Value	Activity instances	Frequency	<input type="checkbox"/> /vgr/pick_up_and_transport	917	29.05%	<input type="checkbox"/> /hbw/unload	299	9.47%	<input type="checkbox"/> /hbw/store_empty_bucket	263	8.33%	<input type="checkbox"/> /wt/pick_up_and_transport	259	8.2%	<input type="checkbox"/> /ov/burn	238	7.54%	<input type="checkbox"/> /hw/human_review	174	5.51%	<input type="checkbox"/> /men/debur	141	4.47%	<input type="checkbox"/> /hbw/get_empty_bucket	134	4.24%	<input type="checkbox"/> /sm/transport	131	4.15%	<input type="checkbox"/> /hbw/store	122	3.86%
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Question 11

Field	Description
Question	<i>How often do actual durations exceed planned durations across activities in the Smart Factory?</i>
Answer	/
Steps taken	/
Output Type	/
Clarity/Interpretability	/
Effort	/
Ease of Use	/
Screenshot or output	/
Evaluator Notes	Tried to locate planned vs. actual duration comparison feature; not available. The tool does not support comparing metadata (additional attributes) per activity.

Question 13

Field	Description																											
Question	<i>Which resources cause the most failures in Smart Factory?</i>																											
Answer	The resource with the most failures is hbw_2 (30 instances, 31.58% of failures)																											
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discover process from log in home folder. 2. Open <i>Activity instances</i> in toolbar. 3. In <i>Attribute</i> dropdown, select <i>lifecycle:state</i>. 4. Filter for <i>failure</i>. 5. Apply filter. 6. In toolbar, open <i>View</i> → <i>Perspective</i> and select <i>Resource</i>. 7. Display resource table. 8. Read values. 																											
Output Type	Process map and table																											
Clarity/Interpretability	5 – Both the table and process map are well-labelled, structured, and easy to interpret.																											
Effort	It has taken 10 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.																											
Ease of Use	5 – The path to the result is intuitive, with no hidden or unintuitive steps. Labels and menus are consistent, reducing friction.																											
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot displays the 'Resource Inspector' window with the following data:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Resource</th> <th>Activity instances</th> <th>Percentage (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>hbw_2</td><td>30</td><td>31.58</td></tr> <tr><td>vgr_1</td><td>25</td><td>26.32</td></tr> <tr><td>wt_1</td><td>18</td><td>18.95</td></tr> <tr><td>vgr_2</td><td>12</td><td>12.63</td></tr> <tr><td>ov_1</td><td>4</td><td>4.21</td></tr> <tr><td>hbw_1</td><td>2</td><td>2.11</td></tr> <tr><td>pm_1</td><td>2</td><td>2.11</td></tr> <tr><td>wt_2</td><td>2</td><td>2.11</td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>To the right of the table is a process map diagram with a 'Download' button below it.</p>	Resource	Activity instances	Percentage (%)	hbw_2	30	31.58	vgr_1	25	26.32	wt_1	18	18.95	vgr_2	12	12.63	ov_1	4	4.21	hbw_1	2	2.11	pm_1	2	2.11	wt_2	2	2.11
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Evaluator Notes																												

Fluxicon Disco

Environment

Operating system:

- Windows 11 Pro
- Version: 21H2
- OS build: 22000.2538

Version:

- Local. Version 4.1.9

License:

- Academic

Dataset:

- An IoT-Enriched Event Log for Process Mining in Smart Factories [1].

Documentation review

Data Management

Disco supports ingestion of CSV, Excel, MXML, and XES formats with intelligent mapping. It detects timestamp formats automatically, supports millisecond precision, handles multiple timestamp columns, and imports datasets with millions of events. Data preparation is enabled through high-performance filtering, including timeframe, variation, performance, endpoint, attribute, and follower filters. Additional features include project management, dataset copies, notes, anonymization, and export in multiple formats [4], [5], [6].

Score: 4. Based on documentation review, Disco supports multiple types of imports with automatic timestamp detection, millisecond precision, and filtering. It handles millions of events and includes anonymization and export options. The main limitation is the lack of streaming or live data connections, which reduces adaptability for continuous scenarios.

Process Discovery

Disco automatically creates process maps from raw logs using an improved version of Fuzzy Miner. It allows adjusting the abstraction level, filtering directly from map elements, and overlaying multiple process metrics. Animations are available to visualize execution flow over time [4], [5], [6].

Score: 5. Documentation indicates Disco generates process maps automatically. Users can adjust abstraction levels, overlay metrics, and animate flows over time. Functionality is comprehensive for its intended use, though it relies on a single discovery method rather than offering multiple algorithms.

Conformance Checking

Disco does not provide direct model-versus-log conformance checking. Instead, it supports indirect conformance analysis by comparing discovered process variants with expectations and applying filters to identify deviations [4], [5], [6].

Score: 1. According to vendor resources, Disco does not provide formal model-to-log conformance. Deviations can only be examined indirectly by filtering discovered variants and attributes. This enables exploratory checks but does not support structured frameworks such as token replay or alignments.

Process Analysis

Disco provides detailed statistics on activity frequency, durations, waiting times, resource performance, case variants, and throughput. It supports bottleneck identification through animations and metric overlays and allows drill-down to individual cases and events [4], [5], [6].

Score: 4. Documentation shows Disco provides descriptive statistics on frequencies, durations, waiting times, and resources, along with bottleneck visualization and case drill-downs. It lacks predictive or prescriptive methods such as forecasting or simulation, which limits use in advanced analytics.

Monitoring and Reporting

Disco supports manual re-import of updated logs for repeated analysis. Charts and tables can be exported in multiple formats, including CSV, PNG, and PDF. There is no native functionality for live monitoring or scheduled reporting [4], [5], [6].

Score: 2. Based on documentation review, Disco supports export of charts and tables in several formats for reporting. However, it does not provide live dashboards, automation, or integration with external monitoring systems.

Support

Disco includes integrated help with contextual sticky notes, a sandbox project, and built-in feedback tools. It is supported by comprehensive documentation provided by the vendor, and assistance through email and feedback channels [4], [5], [6].

Score: 5. Based on documentation review, Disco offers in-app tutorials, contextual help, and structured vendor documentation. Users also have access to direct support channels. Vendor-provided support ensures reliable onboarding and issue resolution.

Task-based Evaluation

Question 1

Field	Description
Question	What is the most frequent path in Smart Factory process that does not result in failure and includes at least two activities (excluding start/end activities)?
Answer	The most frequent non-failing variant with at least two activities contains 16 activities and occurs in 12 cases.
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open event log. 2. Filter for <i>lifecycle:transition = complete</i>. 3. Exclude <i>lifecycle:state = failure</i>. 4. In the Cases tab, identify the most frequent variant with at least two activities.
Output Type	Table
Clarity/Interpretability	5 - Output is immediately clear. The variants table includes labels, frequency sorting, and tooltips. Links to cases provide direct interpretability
Effort	It has taken 21 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	4 - The workflow is consistent and well-labelled, with functions that are easy to locate and supported by guidance. However, the tool does not automatically filter transitions, requiring an extra step. This minor friction prevents it from being fully effortless.
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows the Disco tool interface for a process named WF_101_0. On the left, there is a navigation pane with a tree view showing 'Variant 1' through 'Variant 17'. The main area displays a table of process variants. The table has columns for 'Activity', 'Transition', 'Date', 'Time', 'Duration', 'Transition and Time', 'Lifecycle:state', 'Lifecycle:transition', 'Process', 'Event', 'Case', and 'Requested:status'. The table is sorted by frequency, with the most frequent variant (Variant 1) highlighted in blue. This variant consists of 16 activities and occurs in 12 cases. The interface also shows a search bar, a filter icon, and a 'Cases' button.</p>
Evaluator Notes	

Question 2

Field	Description
Question	<i>How many different process variants do exist in Smart Factory?</i>
Answer	143 process variants
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Select and open event log. 2. In Cases tab, read value.
Output Type	Text
Clarity/Interpretability	4 – Output is structured and labelled, but the text size and colour contrast are suboptimal. The result is understandable, though stronger visual cues would improve immediacy.
Effort	It has taken 3 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	4 – Workflow is straightforward and functions are easy to locate. Minor uncertainty remains due to multiple tabs, which prevents a fully effortless experience.
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows the Disco software interface. At the top, there is a header with 'Disco - New project' and a search bar containing 'MainProcess'. Below the header, there are tabs for 'Map', 'Statistics', and 'Cases'. The 'Cases' tab is active, showing a list of cases. The list includes 'Variants (143)', 'Cases (301)', and a specific case 'WF_1106_24' with 14 events. The interface is clean and modern, with a blue and white color scheme.</p>
Evaluator Notes	

Question 3

Field	Description																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																															
Question	Which variant has the longest average execution time from start to end in the Smart Factory with at least two cases?																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																															
Answer	The longest variant contains 19 activities, with an average duration of 17 minutes and 10 seconds. It has 6 cases in total.																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																															
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open event log. 2. Filter for <i>lifecycle:transition = complete</i>. 3. Open <i>Statistics</i> tab, select variants, and sort by mean duration. 4. Identify the first variant with at least two activities. 																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																															
Output Type	Table																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																															
Clarity/Interpretability	5 – The table is well-structured with consistent labels. Average duration is displayed in a standard time format, making the output immediately interpretable without extra calculation.																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																															
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Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot displays the Disco software interface. On the left, there is a navigation pane with various filters. The main area shows a Gantt chart with blue bars representing activities for different variants. Below the Gantt chart, a table lists the variants. The table has columns for Variant Name, Cases, and Average Duration. The variant 'Variant 19' is highlighted in blue, indicating it has the longest average duration of 17:10. The table also shows other variants with their respective case counts and average durations.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Variant Name</th> <th>Cases</th> <th>Average Duration</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>Variant 1</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 2</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 3</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 4</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 5</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 6</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 7</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 8</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 9</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 10</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 11</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 12</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 13</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 14</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> <tr><td>Variant 15</td><td>1</td><td>17:10</td></tr> 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20	1	17:10	Variant 21	1	17:10	Variant 22	1	17:10	Variant 23	1	17:10	Variant 24	1	17:10	Variant 25	1	17:10	Variant 26	1	17:10	Variant 27	1	17:10	Variant 28	1	17:10	Variant 29	1	17:10	Variant 30	1	17:10	Variant 31	1	17:10	Variant 32	1	17:10	Variant 33	1	17:10	Variant 34	1	17:10	Variant 35	1	17:10	Variant 36	1	17:10	Variant 37	1	17:10	Variant 38	1	17:10	Variant 39	1	17:10	Variant 40	1	17:10	Variant 41	1	17:10	Variant 42	1	17:10	Variant 43	1	17:10	Variant 44	1	17:10	Variant 45	1	17:10	Variant 46	1	17:10	Variant 47	1	17:10	Variant 48	1	17:10	Variant 49	1	17:10	Variant 50	1	17:10	Variant 51	1	17:10	Variant 52	1	17:10	Variant 53	1	17:10	Variant 54	1	17:10	Variant 55	1	17:10	Variant 56	1	17:10	Variant 57	1	17:10	Variant 58	1	17:10	Variant 59	1	17:10	Variant 60	1	17:10	Variant 61	1	17:10	Variant 62	1	17:10	Variant 63	1	17:10	Variant 64	1	17:10	Variant 65	1	17:10	Variant 66	1	17:10	Variant 67	1	17:10	Variant 68	1	17:10	Variant 69	1	17:10	Variant 70	1	17:10	Variant 71	1	17:10	Variant 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Evaluator Notes																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																

Question 4

Field	Description
Question	<i>What is the average number of activities per case in the Smart Factory process?</i>
Answer	/
Steps taken	/
Output Type	/
Clarity/Interpretability	/
Effort	/
Ease of Use	/
Screenshot or output	
Evaluator Notes	We can see events per case but we have to manually calculate the average.

Question 5

Field	Description
Question	<i>Which activity shows the highest deviation in its execution duration across cases in the Smart Factory?</i>
Answer	
Steps taken	
Output Type	
Clarity/Interpretability	
Effort	
Ease of Use	
Screenshot or output	
Evaluator Notes	No information of duration deviation per activity is found in the tool.

Question 6

Field	Description														
Question	<i>What is average time for case completion in Smart Factory?</i>														
Answer	8.7 minutes.														
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Filter for <i>lifecycle:transition = complete</i>. 3. Open <i>Statistics</i> tab and read value. 														
Output Type	Text														
Clarity/Interpretability	5 - The statistic is directly labelled, clearly associated with its measure, and immediately understandable.														
Effort	It has taken 12 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.														
Ease of Use	5 - The workflow is intuitive and consistent. The interface makes the result easy to obtain with minimal effort.														
Screenshot or output	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>Events</td> <td>3,157</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Cases</td> <td>301</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Activities</td> <td>21</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Median case duration</td> <td>8.5 mins</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mean case duration</td> <td>8.7 mins</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Start</td> <td>06/23/2021 17:32:23</td> </tr> <tr> <td>End</td> <td>02/27/2022 18:15:25</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Events	3,157	Cases	301	Activities	21	Median case duration	8.5 mins	Mean case duration	8.7 mins	Start	06/23/2021 17:32:23	End	02/27/2022 18:15:25
Events	3,157														
Cases	301														
Activities	21														
Median case duration	8.5 mins														
Mean case duration	8.7 mins														
Start	06/23/2021 17:32:23														
End	02/27/2022 18:15:25														
Evaluator Notes															

Question 7

Field	Description
Question	<i>How many cases have a total duration longer than twice the average case duration in Smart Factory?</i>
Answer	25 cases.
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Filter for <i>lifecycle:transition = complete</i>. 3. Open <i>Statistics</i> tab and read average duration (≈ 8.7 minutes). 4. Apply <i>Performance</i> filter with threshold = 17 minutes. 5. Read number of cases.
Output Type	Text
Clarity/Interpretability	4 - Output is clearly labelled and structured, but the case count display is small and visually understated. Stronger visual cues would improve immediacy.
Effort	It has taken 15 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	4 - The workflow is clear and consistent. Setting a manual threshold introduces minor friction, so the process is smooth but not entirely effortless.
Screenshot or output	
Evaluator Notes	

Question 8

Field	Description
Question	Which is the longest path for a case in Smart Factory.
Answer	The longest path contains 23 activities . Two cases follow this path: WF_104_18 and WF_102_35 .
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Filter for <i>lifecycle:transition = complete</i>. 3. Open <i>Statistics</i> tab and sort by event count. 4. Read the longest paths from the table.
Output Type	Table
Clarity/Interpretability	5 - The table is structured, labelled, and directly displays the number of activities. The output is immediately understandable without extra calculation.
Effort	It has taken 11 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	5 - The workflow is clear and consistent. Filtering, sorting, and reading results are straightforward, requiring minimal cognitive effort.
Screenshot or output	
Evaluator Notes	

Question 9

Field	Description
Question	<i>To what extent do cases under process model WF_101 comply with the defined process model WF_101?</i>
Answer	
Steps taken	
Output Type	
Clarity/Interpretability	
Effort	
Ease of Use	
Screenshot or output	
Evaluator Notes	The tool does not feature BPMN conformance checking.

Question 11

Field	Description
Question	<i>How often do actual durations exceed planned durations across activities in the Smart Factory?</i>
Answer	
Steps taken	
Output Type	
Clarity/Interpretability	
Effort	
Ease of Use	
Screenshot or output	
Evaluator Notes	No functionality was found that would be able to help answering this question.

Question 12

Field	Description
Question	Which activity has the highest total execution time in the Smart Factory process?
Answer	The activity with the highest total execution time is /vgr/pick_up_and_transport .
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Filter for <i>lifecycle:transition = complete</i>. 3. In <i>Map</i> tab under <i>Performance</i>, select <i>Total duration</i>. 4. Read value from process map.
Output Type	Process map
Clarity/Interpretability	5 - The process map is immediately understandable, with clear labels and color coding. Identifying the activity with the highest duration requires no extra interpretation.
Effort	It has taken 11 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	5 - The workflow is intuitive and consistent. Selecting the overlay and reading the result was seamless.
Screenshot or output	
Evaluator Notes	

Question 13

Field	Description
Question	<i>Which resources cause the most failures in Smart Factory?</i>
Answer	The resource with the most failures is hbw_2 , with 30 failures in total.
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Filter for <i>lifecycle:transition = complete</i>. 3. Filter for <i>lifecycle:state = failure</i>. 4. Open <i>Statistics</i> → <i>Resource</i> view. 5. Read values.
Output Type	Table
Clarity/Interpretability	5 - The resource table is structured and labelled. It is immediately clear which resources cause the most failures.
Effort	It has taken 18 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	5 - The workflow is consistent and intuitive. Filtering and switching to the resource view was straightforward and required minimal cognitive effort.
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot displays the Disco Resource view. At the top, there is a chart showing resource usage over time. Below the chart is a table with columns for 'Resource', 'Property', 'Priority', 'Failure frequency', 'Mean duration', 'Max duration', and 'Standard range'. The resource 'hbw_2' is highlighted in blue and has the highest failure frequency of 30. Other resources listed include 'hbw_1', 'hbw_3', 'hbw_4', 'hbw_5', 'hbw_6', 'hbw_7', 'hbw_8', 'hbw_9', 'hbw_10', 'hbw_11', 'hbw_12', 'hbw_13', 'hbw_14', 'hbw_15', 'hbw_16', 'hbw_17', 'hbw_18', 'hbw_19', 'hbw_20', 'hbw_21', 'hbw_22', 'hbw_23', 'hbw_24', 'hbw_25', 'hbw_26', 'hbw_27', 'hbw_28', 'hbw_29', 'hbw_30', 'hbw_31', 'hbw_32', 'hbw_33', 'hbw_34', 'hbw_35', 'hbw_36', 'hbw_37', 'hbw_38', 'hbw_39', 'hbw_40', 'hbw_41', 'hbw_42', 'hbw_43', 'hbw_44', 'hbw_45', 'hbw_46', 'hbw_47', 'hbw_48', 'hbw_49', 'hbw_50'.</p>
Evaluator Notes	

ProM

Environment

Operating system:

- Windows 11 Pro
- Version: 21H2
- OS build: 22000.2538

Dataset:

- https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Dataset_An_IoT-Enriched_Event_Log_for_Process_Mining_in_Smart_Factories/20130794

Version:

- Local. Version 6.14

License:

- GNU GPLv2

Dataset:

- An IoT-Enriched Event Log for Process Mining in Smart Factories [1].

Documentation review

All assessments are based on inspection of official documentation, vendor resources, and publicly available tutorials. Scores reflect the functionality described in these sources rather than hands-on testing.

Data Management

ProM 6.14 supports importing event logs in the XES format, the IEEE standard for process mining. Conversion from legacy sources is enabled through the ProM Import Framework and XESame, which allows mapping attributes from databases or files into XES. Logs can also be filtered, merged, and transformed using a range of plug-ins, and outputs can be exported for further analysis [7], [8], [9], [10].

Score: 3. Based on documentation review, ProM supports XES logs as the primary standard and enables conversion from databases or legacy sources using XESame and the Import Framework. Filtering and transformation are available through plug-ins. Functionality is flexible but fragmented reducing ease of use compared to integrated solutions.

Process Discovery

ProM includes a wide selection of discovery algorithms, such as Alpha Miner, Heuristics Miner, ILP Miner, Genetic Miner, and Fuzzy Miner. These generate models including Petri nets, transition systems, and heuristic nets. Examples show that results vary depending on the algorithm chosen, allowing both experimental exploration and applied discovery [7], [8], [9], [10], [11].

Score: 5. Documentation indicates ProM supports a wide range of discovery algorithms, including Alpha, Heuristics, ILP, Genetic, and Fuzzy miners, generating Petri nets, heuristic

nets, and other models. The variety of approaches covers all major discovery methods and enables both experimental and applied use.

Conformance Checking

ProM supports conformance checking through plug-ins implementing alignment-based methods, token replay, and deviation analysis. These allow comparison of event logs against process models with visual and quantitative outputs. Resources illustrate how users can measure fitness and identify deviations between observed and intended behaviour [8], [9], [10], [11].

Score: 4. According to inspected resources, ProM supports token replay, alignment-based checking, and deviation analysis. Results are visualized and quantified, enabling fitness measurement. Functionality is extensive, though distributed across separate plug-ins, which increases complexity.

Process Analysis

ProM offers a variety of analysis plug-ins, including performance analysis, dotted chart visualization, resource and organizational mining, and social network mining. These allow users to investigate timing, workload, and resource interactions from different perspectives [8], [9], [10], [11].

Score: 4. Documentation shows ProM includes plug-ins for performance analysis, dotted charts, social network mining, and organizational analysis. This breadth supports multiple analytical perspectives. However, like conformance checking, features are fragmented and require familiarity with the environment.

Monitoring and Reporting

ProM is designed for offline analysis of event logs. It does not provide continuous monitoring or automated reporting. Results can be visualized within plug-ins and exported, but there are no dashboards or live data connections [7], [8], [9], [10], [11].

Score: 1. Based on documentation review, ProM is designed for offline use. Users can generate static visualizations and exports, but there are no dashboards, live data connections, or automated reporting functions.

Support

Documentation is available in the form of academic papers, the official website, and tutorials. Users can also access learning resources through examples and exercises, but there is no commercial vendor support or structured training. ProM also has community forum [7], [8], [9], [10], [11].

Score: 2. Documentation and tutorials are maintained by the research community. Resources include academic papers, examples, and exercises, but structured vendor support is absent. This provides basic learning support but limited guidance for practical adoption.

Task-based Evaluation

Question 1

Field	Description
Question	<i>What is the most frequent path in Smart Factory process that does not result in failure and includes at least two activities (excluding start/end activities)?</i>
Answer	The most frequent non-failing path with at least two activities contains 16 activities and occurs in 12 cases.
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Select event log. 2. Open actions tab for chosen log. 3. Apply <i>Filter events based on attribute values</i> plug-in. 4. Select all event classes. 5. Choose <i>lifecycle:transition</i> as filter attribute. 6. Filter for <i>scheduled</i> and <i>start</i> values. 7. Use <i>Event Filter on Event Log</i> visualization. 8. Add filter <i>Project traces on events by event attributes</i> and exclude <i>lifecycle:state = failure</i>. 9. Read resulting values.
Output Type	Visualisation and text
Clarity/Interpretability	4 – The variant visualization is structured and labelled, with colour coding that highlights repeated activities. However, the interface displays multiple panels and technical details simultaneously, creating visual clutter.
Effort	It has taken 25 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	2 – Navigation and workflows were confusing. Labels and steps were inconsistent, and functions were difficult to locate.
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows a web-based interface for analyzing event logs. At the top, there's a search bar and a title 'Anonymous log imported from MainProcess.xls - Filtered on lifecycle:transition'. Below this, there are several tabs: 'Filter Events', 'Event Log', 'Event Filter', 'Event Log Visualization', and 'Event Log Table'. The 'Filter Events' tab is active, showing a list of event classes with a 'Click to add a filter' button. The 'Event Log Visualization' tab is also visible, showing a horizontal bar chart with colored bars representing different activities. The 'Event Log Table' tab is also visible, showing a table with columns for 'Event Class', 'Time', 'User', and 'Value'. The table contains several rows of data, including 'Event Class', 'Time', 'User', and 'Value'.</p>
Evaluator Notes	

Question 2

Field	Description																
Question	<i>How many different process variants do exist in Smart Factory?</i>																
Answer	143 process variants.																
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Open actions tab. 3. Apply <i>Filter events based on attribute values</i> plug-in. 4. Select all event classes. 5. Choose <i>lifecycle:transition</i> as filter attribute. 6. Filter for <i>scheduled</i> and <i>start</i> values. 7. Open <i>Event Filter on Event Log</i> visualization. 8. Read values. 																
Output Type	Text																
Clarity	4 – Output is labelled, but the font is small and the table lacks grid lines, making it harder to follow rows. The result is interpretable without external help, but not fully effortless.																
Effort	It has taken 15 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.																
Ease of Use	3 - The task was achievable but required noticeable mental load due to non-intuitive workflows and inconsistent layout. Some steps were clear, but overall navigation was uneven.																
Screenshot or output	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>Traces</td> <td>301</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Events</td> <td>3,157</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Event Classes</td> <td>21</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Attributes</td> <td>18</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Variants</td> <td>143</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Events per Trace</td> <td>10,488</td> </tr> <tr> <td>First Event</td> <td>2021-06-23T15:33:16Z</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Last Event</td> <td>2022-02-27T17:15:25Z</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Traces	301	Events	3,157	Event Classes	21	Attributes	18	Variants	143	Events per Trace	10,488	First Event	2021-06-23T15:33:16Z	Last Event	2022-02-27T17:15:25Z
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Last Event	2022-02-27T17:15:25Z																
Evaluator Notes																	

Question 3

Field	Description
Question	<i>Which variant has the longest average execution time from start to end in the Smart Factory with at least two cases?</i>
Answer	
Steps taken	
Output Type	
Clarity/Interpretability	
Effort	
Ease of Use	
Screenshot or output	
Evaluator Notes	We were unable to filter variants based on average execution time.

Question 4

Field	Description
Question	What is the average number of activities per case in the Smart Factory process?
Answer	The average number of activities per case is 10 .
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Open actions tab. 3. Apply <i>Filter events based on attribute values</i> plug-in. 4. Select all event classes. 5. Choose <i>lifecycle:transition</i> as filter attribute. 6. Filter for <i>scheduled</i> and <i>start</i> values. 7. Read values.
Output Type	Text and visualisation
Clarity/Interpretability	5 - The output is clearly labelled and structured. Both the text and visual representation convey the result directly, without ambiguity.
Effort	It has taken 13 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	3 - The task is achievable, but the workflow is fragmented and requires noticeable mental focus. Some elements are clear, but overall navigation is not streamlined.
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot displays a dashboard with a sidebar on the left containing navigation icons and a main area with two stacked bar charts. The top chart is titled 'Events per case' and shows a distribution of event counts per case, with a mean of 10. The bottom chart is titled 'Event classes per case' and shows the distribution of event classes per case, with a mean of 8. A 'Log info' panel on the right provides system details.</p>
Evaluator Notes	

Question 5

Field	Description
Question	<i>Which activity shows the highest deviation in its execution duration across cases in the Smart Factory?</i>
Answer	The activity with the highest deviation is /sm/transport .
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Open actions tab. 3. Apply <i>Filter events based on attribute values</i> plug-in. 4. Select all event classes. 5. Choose <i>lifecycle:transition</i> as filter attribute. 6. Exclude <i>scheduled</i> and <i>start</i> values. 7. Open <i>Inductive Visual Miner</i> visualization. 8. Select <i>Data Analysis</i>. 9. In <i>Model Time</i> tab, choose time type = <i>sojourn time</i> and property = <i>standard deviation</i>. 10. Sort on <i>All traces</i> and read the values.
Output Type	Table
Clarity/Interpretability	5 - The table is structured, values are labelled, and the output directly shows standard deviations without ambiguity.
Effort	It has taken 25 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	2 - The workflow is fragmented, requiring multiple nested steps and detailed configuration. Navigation is not intuitive, and completing the task involved high cognitive load.

Screenshot or output

The screenshot shows the 'Data analysis - visual Miner' interface. The 'Model time' tab is active, displaying a table titled 'Analyse the time spent in model activities.' The table has four columns: 'Model part', 'time type', 'property', and 'all traces'. The data is as follows:

Model part	time type	property	all traces
/sm/transport	sojourn time	standard deviation	0d 00:04:06:477
/hw/human_review	"	"	0d 00:03:51:714
/mm/deburr	"	"	0d 00:03:23:918
/wt/pick_up_and_transport	"	"	0d 00:02:44:025
/ov/burn	"	"	0d 00:01:56:761
/vgr/pick_up_and_transport	"	"	0d 00:01:31:947
/hbw/store_empty_bucket	"	"	0d 00:01:12:892
/ov/temper	"	"	0d 00:00:47:096
/pm/punch_gill	"	"	0d 00:00:39:036
/sm/sort	"	"	0d 00:00:30:834
/mm/mill	"	"	0d 00:00:27:402
/hbw/get_empty_bucket	"	"	0d 00:00:26:018
/hbw/store	"	"	0d 00:00:13:585
/pm/punch_recesses	"	"	0d 00:00:11:639
/dm/lower	"	"	0d 00:00:10:290
/pm/punch_ribbing	"	"	0d 00:00:09:888
/mm/drill	"	"	0d 00:00:06:284

At the bottom of the table, there are filters: 'Show: Model part [all]', 'time type sojourn time', 'property standard deviation'.

Evaluator Notes

Question 6

Field	Description
Question	<i>What is average time for case completion in Smart Factory?</i>
Answer	8 minutes and 1 second.
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Open actions tab. 3. Apply <i>Filter events based on attribute values</i> plug-in. 4. Select all event classes. 5. Choose <i>lifecycle:transition</i> as filter attribute. 6. Exclude <i>scheduled</i> and <i>start</i> values. 7. Open <i>Inductive Visual Miner</i> visualization. 8. Select <i>Data Analysis</i>. 9. Read average duration in <i>Trace attributes</i>.
Output Type	Text
Clarity/Interpretability	4 – The output is labelled and interpretable, but lacks supporting visual cues such as colour coding or hierarchical styling. This prevents full immediacy.
Effort	It has taken 17 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.
Ease of Use	3 - The task was achievable, but navigation was fragmented. Multiple steps and view changes introduced noticeable cognitive load.
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows a software window titled "Data analysis - visual Mi...". It has several tabs: "Cost model", "Associations", "Causal", "Event attributes", "Model time", and "Cohort analysis". The "Trace attributes" tab is active, showing a table with columns "Attribute", "property", and "value". The table lists various attributes like "conceptname", "duration", "maximum", "median", "minimum", and "standard deviation". A histogram is displayed for the "duration" attribute, showing a distribution of values. The window also includes a "Show: Attribute" dropdown menu at the bottom.</p>
Evaluator Notes	

Question 7

Field	Description																
Question	<i>How many cases have a total duration longer than twice the average case duration in Smart Factory?</i>																
Answer	25 cases.																
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Open actions tab. 3. Apply <i>Filter events based on attribute values</i> plug-in. 4. Select all event classes. 5. Choose <i>lifecycle:transition</i> as filter attribute. 6. Exclude <i>scheduled</i> and <i>start</i> values. 7. Open <i>Inductive Visual Miner</i>. 8. Select <i>Data Analysis</i> and read average duration (8 minutes). 9. Open <i>Event Filter on Event Log</i> visualization. 10. Apply <i>Select traces by performance</i> filter with threshold = 16 minutes. 11. Read number of cases. 																
Output Type	Text																
Clarity/Interpretability	4 - Output is labelled and structured, but lacks visual separation (lines, shading) that would improve readability.																
Effort	It has taken 26 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.																
Ease of Use	2 - The workflow is fragmented and spread across different visualizations. Manual configuration and multiple switches increased cognitive load and made navigation cumbersome.																
Screenshot or output	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>Traces</td> <td>25</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Events</td> <td>408</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Event Classes</td> <td>18</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Attributes</td> <td>19</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Variants</td> <td>23</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Events per Trace</td> <td>16.32</td> </tr> <tr> <td>First Event</td> <td>2021-06-25T09:51:39Z</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Last Event</td> <td>2021-07-08T18:22:29Z</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Traces	25	Events	408	Event Classes	18	Attributes	19	Variants	23	Events per Trace	16.32	First Event	2021-06-25T09:51:39Z	Last Event	2021-07-08T18:22:29Z
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Events per Trace	16.32																
First Event	2021-06-25T09:51:39Z																
Last Event	2021-07-08T18:22:29Z																
Evaluator Notes																	

Question 8

Field	Description																								
Question	<i>Which is the longest path for a case in Smart Factory?</i>																								
Answer	The two longest paths are WF_104_18 and WF_102_35 , each with 23 activities.																								
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Open actions tab. 3. Apply <i>Filter events based on attribute values</i> plug-in. 4. Select all event classes. 5. Choose <i>lifecycle:transition</i> as filter attribute. 6. Exclude <i>scheduled</i> and <i>start</i> values. 7. Open <i>Event Filter on Event Log</i> visualization. 8. Toggle full screen mode. 9. Sort by length (descending). 10. Read values. 																								
Output Type	Visualisation and text																								
Clarity/Interpretability	3 - The coloured blocks show the case path, but the tool does not provide an explicit count of activities. The analyst must manually count them.																								
Effort	It has taken 18 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.																								
Ease of Use	3 - The process is not streamlined. Multiple manual steps and the need to count activities introduce noticeable cognitive effort.																								
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows a software interface for analyzing event logs. The main area displays a visualization of case paths, where each path is represented by a horizontal bar composed of colored segments. A table at the bottom provides details for a selected case, including its ID, time, event name, and value.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1029 1534 1209 1601"> <thead> <tr> <th>Case</th> <th>Time</th> <th>Event Name</th> <th>Value</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>WF_104_18</td> <td>2017-08-21 10:13:02</td> <td>lifecycle:transition</td> <td>start</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Case	Time	Event Name	Value	WF_104_18	2017-08-21 10:13:02	lifecycle:transition	start	WF_104_18	2017-08-21 10:13:02	lifecycle:transition	start	WF_104_18	2017-08-21 10:13:02	lifecycle:transition	start	WF_104_18	2017-08-21 10:13:02	lifecycle:transition	start	WF_104_18	2017-08-21 10:13:02	lifecycle:transition	start
Case	Time	Event Name	Value																						
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WF_104_18	2017-08-21 10:13:02	lifecycle:transition	start																						
Evaluator Notes																									

Question 9

Field	Description
Question	<i>To what extent do cases under process model WF_101 comply with the defined process model WF_101?</i>
Answer	
Steps taken	
Output Type	
Feature Coverage	
Clarity/Interpretability	
Effort	
Ease of Use	
Screenshot or output	
Evaluator Notes	No plugin supports conformance checking with the provided BPMN

Question 10

Field	Description																								
Question	<i>What is the most common activity in the Smart Factory process and how often does it occur?</i>																								
Answer	The most common activity is /vgr/pick_up_and_transport with 917 occurrences.																								
Steps taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Load event log. 2. Open actions tab. 3. Apply <i>Filter events based on attribute values</i> plug-in. 4. Select all event classes. 5. Choose <i>lifecycle:transition</i> as filter attribute. 6. Exclude <i>scheduled</i> and <i>start</i> values. 7. Open <i>Summary</i> tab. 8. Read activity frequencies. 																								
Output Type	Table																								
Clarity/Interpretability	4 - The table is labelled and structured, but the absence of grid lines or visual separation makes scanning rows less comfortable.																								
Effort	It has taken 14 clicks in total to get the result for the given question.																								
Ease of Use	4- The workflow is consistent and the result easy to locate. Some friction remains due to repeated filtering steps, but overall the process required little mental load.																								
Screenshot or output	<p>The screenshot shows a 'Log Summary' window with the following data:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Class</th> <th>Occurrences (absolute)</th> <th>Occurrences (relative)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>/vgr/pick_up_and_transport</td> <td>917</td> <td>29.047%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>thehumanload</td> <td>299</td> <td>9.471%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>thehuman_pick_up_and_transport</td> <td>203</td> <td>6.391%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>thehuman_pick_up_and_transport</td> <td>203</td> <td>6.391%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>thehuman</td> <td>238</td> <td>7.539%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>thehuman_review</td> <td>174</td> <td>5.512%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>thehuman</td> <td>141</td> <td>4.405%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Class	Occurrences (absolute)	Occurrences (relative)	/vgr/pick_up_and_transport	917	29.047%	thehumanload	299	9.471%	thehuman_pick_up_and_transport	203	6.391%	thehuman_pick_up_and_transport	203	6.391%	thehuman	238	7.539%	thehuman_review	174	5.512%	thehuman	141	4.405%
Class	Occurrences (absolute)	Occurrences (relative)																							
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thehuman	238	7.539%																							
thehuman_review	174	5.512%																							
thehuman	141	4.405%																							
Evaluator Notes																									

Question 11

Field	Description
Question	<i>How often do actual durations exceed planned durations across activities in the Smart Factory?</i>
Answer	
Steps taken	
Output Type	
Feature Coverage	
Clarity/Interpretability	
Effort	
Ease of Use	
Screenshot or output	
Evaluator Notes	Unable to answer with ProM tool

Question 12

Field	Description
Question	<i>Which activity has the highest total execution time in the Smart Factory process?</i>
Answer	
Steps taken	
Output Type	
Feature Coverage	
Clarity/Interpretability	
Effort	
Ease of Use	
Screenshot or output	
Evaluator Notes	

Sources

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